

The Effect of Religious Education on Political Economy: A Case of Selected Secondary Schools in Lusaka District, Zambia

**Chanda Chansa Thelma¹, Zohaib Hassan Sain², Edwin Vinandi Phiri³,
Mwila Mwenda Gilbert⁴**

¹Chreso University, Lusaka, Zambia, Department of Humanities and Social Sciences

²Superior University, Lahore, Pakistan, Faculty of Business & Management Sciences

³Kafwimbi Day Secondary School, Isoka, Zambia, Department of Education and Social Sciences

⁴Rockview University, Lusaka, Zambia, Department of ECE and Primary Education

Corresponding Author: tchanda@chresouniversity.edu.zm

Abstract:

The study investigated the effect of religious education on the political economy, with a focus on selected secondary schools in Lusaka district of Zambia. Religious education, often viewed as an instrument of moral and ethical instruction, plays a critical role in shaping students' beliefs and attitudes towards political and economic systems. This study explored how religious teachings embedded within the curriculum influence students' understanding of governance, economic justice, social responsibility, and leadership. The study adopted a mixed methods approach which is a combination of quantitative and qualitative data. The study focused on selected secondary schools in Lusaka District, Zambia, representing urban and peri-urban settings with diverse socio-economic and religious backgrounds with a sample of 150 respondents. Data were collected from head teachers, teachers, students, and community members through a combination of interviews, and questionnaires. The quantitative data collected through the questionnaires were analyzed using appropriate statistical methods, such as descriptive statistics using SPSS (statistical package for social sciences) and excel whereas the qualitative data from semi structured interviews were analyzed thematically. The findings revealed that religious education has a profound impact on shaping students' ethical frameworks, often promoting ideals of fairness, integrity, and social justice, which translate into their political and economic viewpoints. However, the study also identified a complex duality in the outcomes: while religious teachings can encourage democratic participation and a sense of responsibility towards societal welfare, they can also reinforce traditional power structures and potentially conflict with modern political ideologies like liberalism and secularism. The study therefore recommended that schools should organize interfaith dialogues and civic engagement initiatives that encourage students to explore the practical applications of religious principles in addressing political and economic challenges.

Keywords: Civic Engagement, Governance, Political Economy, Religious Education, and Socio-Economic Justice.

1. INTRODUCTION

Religion and politics have always been intertwined, influencing the social, cultural, and economic dynamics of societies around the world. The role of religion in shaping individuals' beliefs, values, and behaviors has been well-documented. Similarly, political economy examines the interplay between politics and economics, exploring how political systems and economic structures influence one another (Chanda, 2024a). This research proposal aimed to investigate the effect of religious education on political economy, specifically examining how religious teachings and values impact economic decision-making, policy formation, and socio-economic outcomes. Religious education is an integral part of the curriculum in many educational systems, aiming to impart religious knowledge, values, and ethics to students (Johnson, 2017). In Zambia, a predominantly Christian country, religious education holds a significant place within the educational framework (Mweetwa & Malama, 2016). However, the impact of religious education on political and economic perspectives remains a topic of interest and debate.

Political economy, the intersection of politics and economics, is a field that examines how political systems and government policies influence economic activities and outcomes (Stiglitz, 2018). Within the context of education, religious teachings and beliefs can shape students' understanding of political and economic systems (Ecklund & Scheitle, 2017). Religious education plays a crucial role in molding individuals' moral and ethical values, which can extend to their views on political ideologies and economic principles (Hunt, 2019). Understanding the effects of religious education on political economy is crucial due to its potential implications for national development. As religion can impact individuals' perspectives on governance, wealth distribution, and social justice (Deneulin & Bano, 2019), it is vital to assess whether religious education promotes or hinders positive attitudes towards inclusive economic policies, transparent governance, and equitable development strategies.

One aspect to consider is how religious education influences students' political awareness and their subsequent participation in political processes. There is a need to examine whether religious education fosters an understanding of political structures, systems, and ideologies, and whether it motivates students to engage in political discussions, express their opinions, and actively participate in civic activities (Campbell, 2017; Teymoori et al., 2018). An important aspect of examining the influence of religious education on political awareness and participation is determining whether it motivates students to engage in political discussions, express their opinions, and actively participate in civic activities. Religious education has the potential to provide a moral framework that inspires students to become active and engaged citizens. It may encourage them to critically analyze political issues, voice their perspectives, and contribute to the public discourse on matters of social importance (Chanda, 2024b). Moreover, religious institutions often play a significant role in community development and social activism, which can influence students' motivation to participate in political processes. By exploring the extent to which religious education encourages students to actively engage in political discussions and civic activities, this

research can shed light on the potential role of religious education in nurturing a generation of politically aware and participatory individuals.

Religious teachings often encompass moral and ethical principles that can shape individuals' economic perspectives and decision-making. Investigating the impact of religious education on students' attitudes towards economic issues, such as wealth redistribution, income inequality, entrepreneurship, and ethical business practices, can provide insights into how religious education influences the formation of economic values and behavior (Brañas-Garza et al., 2016; DellaPosta et al., 2018).

Religious education can also influence students' perspectives on entrepreneurship and ethical business practices. Religious teachings often advocate for principles such as honesty, integrity, and social responsibility, which can impact students' understanding of economic activities and their ethical implications (Chanda et al., 2024a). For example, religious education may emphasize the importance of conducting business ethically, treating employees fairly, and considering the broader social and environmental consequences of economic decisions. Such teachings may shape students' attitudes towards entrepreneurship, fostering a mindset that prioritizes ethical business practices and sustainable economic development. Exploring the effect of religious education on students' attitudes towards entrepreneurship and ethical business practices can provide insights into the potential role of religious education in shaping responsible economic behavior and promoting sustainable economic growth. Chaves (2020) says that religious education can significantly contribute to the development of individuals' beliefs, values, and ideologies. Understanding how religious education influences the formation of political and economic beliefs among secondary school students is crucial in assessing the potential long-term effects on society, including the alignment of religious teachings with political ideologies and economic systems (Jelen & Wilcox, 2020; Freston, 2019).

Religious education also has the potential to shape individuals' economic beliefs and ideologies. The moral and ethical principles embedded in religious teachings can influence students' views on economic systems, economic justice, and the role of economic activities in society. Religious education may advocate for principles such as stewardship, care for the environment, and economic justice, which can shape students' economic beliefs and their views on issues such as wealth distribution, consumption, and sustainable development. Additionally, religious teachings may provide a critique of excessive materialism, promote a sense of communal responsibility, and emphasize the importance of economic activities that benefit the broader society (Chanda, 2023). Understanding the role of religious education in shaping students' economic beliefs is essential for comprehending the potential impact of religious values on economic policies, economic inequality, and sustainable economic development.

It is important to consider the intersectionality of religious education and socioeconomic factors, such as students' socio-economic backgrounds and their influence on political and economic perspectives. Exploring whether religious education exacerbates or mitigates existing socioeconomic inequalities and how it interacts with other factors that shape students' worldview

can provide a comprehensive understanding of the effect of religious education on the political economy (Demerath, 2017; Evans & Evans, 2018). The intersection of religious education and socioeconomic factors also raises questions about the potential role of religious education in exacerbating or mitigating existing socioeconomic inequalities. Religious teachings often emphasize values of compassion, justice, and social welfare, which can have implications for how students perceive and respond to socioeconomic disparities (Chanda & Chitondo, 2023). On one hand, religious education may foster a sense of social responsibility and motivate students from privileged backgrounds to address societal inequalities through activism, philanthropy, or advocacy for policy changes. On the other hand, religious education might inadvertently reinforce existing socioeconomic hierarchies by promoting ideas that justify or legitimize inequalities, such as notions of divine favor or the meritocratic nature of wealth accumulation. By examining the interaction between religious education and socioeconomic factors, this research can shed light on the complex relationship between religious education and socioeconomic inequality, contributing to a deeper understanding of the impact of religious education on the political economy and social dynamics within a given context.

The Lusaka district which is also the capital city of Zambia, represents a unique setting to investigate the effect of religious education on political economy. The district exhibits diverse socio-cultural characteristics, and secondary schools within the region offer religious education as part of their curriculum. Understanding how religious education influences students' political and economic perspectives in this specific context can provide valuable insights for educational policymakers and curriculum developers. Chanda (2023b) noted that despite the presence of religious education in schools, limited research has been conducted to examine its specific impact on political beliefs and economic understanding among secondary school students in the district. By examining the effect of religious education on political economy in this particular setting, the study aimed to contribute to the existing body of knowledge on the influence of religious education on students' political beliefs and economic understanding. The findings of this research can inform educational policies, curriculum development, and teaching practices related to religious education, leading to a more comprehensive understanding of the complex relationship between religion, education, and socio-economic factors.

1.2 Statement of the problem

The integration of religious education in secondary school curricula has often been viewed as a means of fostering moral and ethical development among students. However, its potential impact on broader societal dimensions, such as the political economy, remains underexplored, particularly in the context of Lusaka district, Zambia. Despite the importance of education in shaping civic attitudes and socio-economic perspectives, little is known about how religious education influences students' understanding of governance, civic responsibilities, and economic systems (Boafo-Arthur, 2013). Concerns arise regarding whether the moral and ethical teachings within religious education equip learners with the critical thinking skills necessary for engaging with complex political and economic realities. Furthermore, disparities in how religious education is

implemented across schools may contribute to varying levels of student awareness and engagement in political and economic issues, thereby influencing their capacity to contribute meaningfully to Zambia's democratic and economic development (Chanda et al., 2023). This study sought to examine the relationship between religious education and students' perceptions of political and economic systems, identifying both the opportunities and challenges associated with integrating such curricula in selected secondary schools in Lusaka District.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

- To examine the impact of religious education on students' understanding of political economy concepts in selected secondary schools in Lusaka district.
- To analyze the role of religious education in fostering critical thinking and ethical decision-making among students regarding political and economic issues.

1.4 Conceptual Framework

The study explored the interplay between the curriculum, pedagogy, and the socio-political consciousness of students. Religious education, as an independent variable, is analyzed through its content, teaching methodologies, and alignment with civic ideals. The dependent variable, the political economy, is operationalized as students' understanding of economic policies, governance systems, and their role as active citizens in a democratic society. Mediating variables include cultural, social, and economic contexts that shape the interpretation and application of religious teachings. The framework posits that religious education can promote ethical leadership, social justice, and critical thinking when taught with an emphasis on inclusivity and societal relevance (Chitando, 2015). Conversely, it can reinforce ideological rigidity and political disengagement if overly doctrinal or exclusionary. The study, therefore, sought to evaluate how religious education in selected schools influences students' political and economic awareness, attitudes, and engagement, with Lusaka's diverse socio-economic landscape serving as a moderating variable.

1.5 Significance of the Study

The significance of this study lies in its potential to bridge the knowledge gap regarding the intersection of religious education and its influence on the political economy within secondary schools in Lusaka District, Zambia. By exploring how religious education shapes students' values, attitudes, and behaviors concerning governance, economic participation, and civic responsibility, this research contributes to understanding the broader implications of educational curricula on societal development. It is hoped that the insights from this study can inform policymakers, educators, and curriculum developers on optimizing religious education to foster critical thinking, ethical leadership, and active citizenship among learners. Additionally, it provides a foundation for future research on the role of education in shaping socio-political and economic structures in Zambia.

2. METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a mixed methods approach which is a combination of quantitative and qualitative data. Exploratory and descriptive designs were as well considered appropriate as they also allowed for more flexible strategies of data collection in order to answer the research questions (Banda et al., 2017). This design was deemed to be appropriate as it provided a comprehensive understanding of how religious education influences aspects of political economy among

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secondary school students. The study focused on selected secondary schools in Lusaka District, Zambia, representing urban and peri-urban settings with diverse socio-economic and religious backgrounds. The sample consisted 150 respondents; 10% of the target population 1500. The population for the study was purposefully drawn from the four schools. Purposive sampling procedure was used to select Head teachers (4); one from each selected school, and teachers of RE (16); four from each selected school. On the other hand, simple random sampling procedure was used to select the pupils (100); twenty-five from each selected school and Community members (30). The data collection process involved distributing the questionnaires to the selected participants and conducting individual interviews. The quantitative data collected through the questionnaires were analyzed using appropriate statistical methods, such as descriptive statistics using SPSS (statistical package for social sciences) and excel whereas the qualitative data from semi structured interviews were analyzed thematically. The study avoided pressuring respondents to take part in the research. Alternatively, permission consents, assents were obtained from respondents involved in the research and the research topic was strategically selected to ensure that there was no harm whatsoever to the research respondents. The study also upheld research ethical considerations such as voluntary participation of the respondents, confidentiality, honesty, and right of privacy.

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Impact of Religious Education on Students' Understanding of Political Economy Concepts

According to research findings, religious education, often focusing on ethical principles, social justice, and moral frameworks, can significantly influence students' understanding of political economy concepts. The study found Awareness of Social Justice at 30%, Ethical Foundations in Political Economy to be at 25%, Influence on Decision-Making and Policy Analysis at 20%, Critique of Materialism at 15%, and the least was Historical Contextualization at 10%. The study findings revealed that religious education plays a crucial role in shaping students' awareness of social justice issues, particularly in understanding political economy concepts. In Lusaka district's secondary schools, religious education is integrated into the curriculum to instill values such as equity, fairness, and human dignity, which are fundamental to social justice (Chanda, 2023c). By engaging with religious teachings and ethical principles, students gain insights into the moral dimensions of economic systems, the distribution of resources, and the societal structures that influence poverty and inequality. These teachings foster critical thinking about the balance between economic progress and the well-being of marginalized populations, enhancing students' understanding of the interconnectedness of social, economic, and political systems (Deneulin, 2019).

Through discussions on scriptural texts and religious doctrines, learners are encouraged to examine real-world issues such as income disparity, unemployment, and access to basic services. Chulu (2019) added that this approach helps them relate moral imperatives to the broader context of political economy, bridging the gap between theoretical concepts and their practical implications. Chanda et al (2023b) in their study noted that religious education also empowers students to question and challenge unjust systems, nurturing a sense of responsibility to advocate for systemic

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changes that promote equity and inclusivity. For instance, lessons emphasizing stewardship and the ethical use of resources inspire students to consider how economic policies impact vulnerable groups, aligning their academic learning with values of compassion and justice. Moreover, religious education in secondary schools often incorporates case studies, community engagement, and service-learning projects that expose students to the lived experiences of those affected by economic injustice. These activities enable learners to develop empathy and a deeper appreciation of the socio-economic challenges faced by their communities. As a result, students are better equipped to understand the ethical implications of political economy decisions and recognize the importance of collective action in addressing issues such as wealth inequality and social exclusion.

Moving on, the respondents also indicated that religious education plays a pivotal role in shaping students' ethical perspectives, which are foundational to their understanding of political economy. By integrating moral principles derived from religious teachings, students are encouraged to view economic systems not just as mechanisms for resource allocation but as frameworks that should prioritize human dignity, equity, and social justice (Chileshe, 2018). This ethical grounding enables students to critically analyze economic policies and practices through the lens of fairness and moral accountability, fostering a more nuanced understanding of political economy concepts. One of the teachers expressed that:

“Students may develop a critical understanding of economic policies and practices, assessing their fairness, inclusivity, and moral alignment. For instance, they might question the ethics of income inequality or exploitative labor systems”.

In secondary schools in Lusaka District, religious education promotes values such as honesty, compassion, and responsibility, which are directly applicable to political economy. For instance, discussions on economic inequality and poverty often resonate with teachings about stewardship, care for the marginalized, and the equitable distribution of resources. Chanda et al (2024b) revealed that as students engage with these principles, they develop a heightened awareness of how ethical considerations influence policy decisions, market behaviors, and societal outcomes.

Moreover, religious education encourages critical thinking by presenting ethical dilemmas and case studies that intersect with economic realities. Students explore the consequences of corruption, the ethics of wealth accumulation, and the moral obligations of governments and businesses to ensure social welfare (Deng, 2016). This approach helps bridge theoretical knowledge of political economy with real-world challenges, enabling learners to formulate well-rounded, ethically informed opinions on economic and political issues. The impact of religious education extends to the cultivation of civic responsibility. By instilling a sense of moral duty towards societal improvement, students are motivated to participate in democratic processes and advocate for policies that align with ethical standards (Chanda et al., 2024c). This aligns with the broader aim of political economy education, which seeks to prepare students to navigate and influence complex socio-economic systems for the common good.

The study results further noted that religious education plays a significant role in shaping students' cognitive and ethical perspectives, thereby influencing their decision-making and policy analysis abilities in understanding political economy concepts. By integrating moral and ethical dimensions into the curriculum, religious education encourages students to critically evaluate socio-economic

and political issues. In selected secondary schools in Lusaka District, this approach helps students develop a framework for assessing the fairness, justice, and equity of economic policies and political decisions (Kabwe & Banda, 2016). The ethical teachings embedded in religious education often prompt learners to consider the societal impacts of economic policies, such as resource distribution, poverty alleviation, and social welfare.

Furthermore, religious education fosters critical thinking and analytical skills by encouraging students to engage in debates on ethical dilemmas and real-world challenges. These skills are crucial for understanding and evaluating complex political economy concepts, such as governance, market regulation, and fiscal responsibility (Chanda, 2024c). For instance, lessons on stewardship and community welfare from religious texts can inspire students to consider sustainable and inclusive economic practices when analyzing policies. In addition, religious education promotes values such as empathy, responsibility, and accountability, which are vital in decision-making processes. Students are encouraged to reflect on how their decisions and policy preferences align with broader societal needs and ethical principles. This moral grounding can enhance their ability to make informed and equitable decisions, particularly in scenarios requiring a balance between economic efficiency and social justice (Banerjee & Duflo, 2017).

Moreover, the interdisciplinary nature of religious education enables students to connect ethical teachings with principles of political economy. By examining historical and contemporary examples of governance and economic systems through a moral lens, students gain a deeper understanding of the relationship between economic policies and societal well-being (Kabangila & Banda, 2021). In Lusaka District, this holistic approach has been shown to improve students' ability to analyze policies critically and propose solutions that are both ethical and practical. Overall, the integration of religious education into the curriculum not only enriches students' moral and ethical perspectives but also equips them with the analytical tools needed to understand and influence decision-making and policy analysis in political economy. This impact is particularly evident in the way students approach complex societal issues, demonstrating a nuanced understanding of the interplay between ethics, governance, and economic development.

Head teachers pointed out that in selected secondary schools in Lusaka district, religious teachings often emphasize ethical considerations that challenge the pursuit of wealth at the expense of social and spiritual values. One of the head teachers viewed that:

“Religious perspectives often critique materialism and emphasize spiritual well-being over economic wealth. The responded added that students may apply this critique to assess capitalist systems, understanding alternative economic models that prioritize communal rather than individualistic prosperity”.

Chanda et al (2024d) in their study showed that students exposed to these teachings develop a nuanced understanding of political economy concepts by integrating moral frameworks into their economic reasoning. For instance, religious principles encourage students to evaluate the implications of consumerism and profit-driven motives within economic systems, fostering a more holistic and critical perspective on material wealth and its societal impact.

This critique of materialism also influences how students perceive wealth distribution and social justice. Religious education introduces them to the idea that excessive accumulation of wealth without regard for equity and the welfare of others can lead to societal imbalances. Through

discussions and reflections on moral principles such as compassion, stewardship, and shared responsibility, students begin to question policies and practices that prioritize economic growth over human dignity and ecological sustainability. Djupe & Gilbert (2019) says that this approach encourages them to consider alternative economic models that promote the common good rather than individual gain.

Moreover, the critique of materialism in religious education helps students develop critical thinking skills by exposing them to debates on ethical dilemmas in political economy. They learn to analyze the tension between capitalist incentives and the moral obligations to address poverty and inequality (Chanda, 2024d). By fostering an awareness of the broader ethical implications of economic actions, religious education empowers students to engage with political economy concepts from a perspective that values human welfare above material success. Ultimately, the integration of religious education and political economy concepts equips students with the tools to critique materialism while advocating for ethical and sustainable economic practices. This impact extends beyond academic learning, shaping their attitudes toward social responsibility and community-oriented solutions to economic challenges in Lusaka district and beyond.

The study results also indicated that religious education in selected secondary schools in Lusaka district plays a crucial role in fostering historical contextualization, significantly enhancing students' understanding of political economy concepts. By integrating narratives from sacred texts and historical developments of religious institutions, religious education provides students with a deeper appreciation of the interplay between religion, politics, and economic systems (Mariano, 2021). For instance, students learn about how religious movements have historically influenced political ideologies and economic policies, such as the role of Christianity in the abolition of slavery or the economic implications of Islamic banking principles.

One of the students explained that:

“This historical perspective equips students with the ability to connect past events to contemporary political and economic phenomena. It also enhances their critical thinking skills as they analyze the ethical dimensions of political economy within a moral and spiritual framework”.

Moreover, Chanda (2024e) observed that understanding the historical relationship between religion and governance helps students grasp the foundations of modern economic systems and how religious principles have shaped social welfare policies and equitable resource distribution. Furthermore, religious education encourages students to reflect on the socio-economic challenges faced by communities in historical contexts and draws parallels to current issues. This reflective process cultivates a sense of responsibility and ethical citizenship among learners. By viewing political economy through a historical and religious lens, students are better equipped to engage with complex societal issues in a nuanced and informed manner, fostering a generation of thoughtful leaders and participants in Zambia's socio-economic development.

Figure1: Impact of Religious Education on Students' Understanding of Political Economy Concepts

3.2. The Role of Religious Education in Fostering Critical Thinking and Ethical Decision-Making among Students Regarding Political and Economic Issues

The study findings revealed that ethical decision-making in political contexts requires individuals to apply moral reasoning and critical thinking to assess the implications of policies and actions on society. Political decisions often have far-reaching consequences, influencing governance, justice, and equity. In this light, fostering ethical decision-making involves equipping individuals with the ability to discern right from wrong while considering the broader impact of their choices (Mulenga, 2019). Students exposed to ethical education are more likely to develop values of integrity, accountability, and empathy, which are critical in addressing political and economic challenges. They are taught to weigh the competing interests of stakeholders, prioritize social welfare, and advocate for policies that uphold human dignity and fairness. Furthermore, ethical decision-making skills help students navigate the complexities of political processes, enabling them to challenge corruption, discrimination, and other societal injustices.

Community members alluded that religious education plays a pivotal role in shaping students' moral compass and enhancing their capacity for critical thinking and ethical decision-making in political and economic spheres. Through religious teachings, students are introduced to foundational ethical principles such as justice, compassion, and stewardship, which serve as a framework for analyzing societal issues (Miti & Sichone, 2017). Religious education encourages students to reflect deeply on the moral dimensions of political decisions, promoting an understanding of the interconnectedness between personal values and public responsibilities. By integrating real-world scenarios into discussions, religious education fosters critical thinking by

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challenging students to evaluate diverse perspectives, question biases, and develop reasoned arguments.

Moreover, religious education provides a platform for exploring the ethical implications of economic systems, policies, and practices. It enables students to consider how economic activities affect marginalized communities and the environment, thereby encouraging a more inclusive and sustainable approach to development (Oladosu, 2015). This holistic perspective empowers students to become ethically conscious citizens who can advocate for equitable and just governance. In essence, religious education not only instills moral values but also equips students with the intellectual tools to navigate and influence political and economic structures ethically. Additionally, the respondents noted that religious education plays a pivotal role in instilling moral responsibility among students, equipping them with the tools to critically engage with political and economic issues. By incorporating ethical principles rooted in religious teachings, educators can foster an environment where students are encouraged to reflect on the broader implications of their decisions and actions. Through the study of moral frameworks and the examination of real-world scenarios, students learn to assess political and economic challenges not just from a practical standpoint but also from an ethical perspective (Chanda, 2023d). This approach cultivates a sense of accountability and encourages students to consider the welfare of others in their decision-making processes.

One of the critical aspects of religious education is its potential to nurture critical thinking skills. By engaging with diverse religious and moral philosophies, students are exposed to multiple perspectives, which helps them develop the ability to analyze and evaluate complex situations. For instance, when confronted with political corruption or economic inequality, students trained in moral reasoning are more likely to question the status quo and propose solutions grounded in fairness and justice (Osman, 2016). This critical engagement prepares them to navigate the moral dilemmas they may encounter in real-life political and economic contexts.

Religious education also emphasizes the development of ethical decision-making, guiding students to align their choices with core values such as integrity, compassion, and respect for human dignity. This alignment is particularly significant in addressing political and economic issues, as these fields often present conflicts between personal gain and societal well-being. By drawing from religious teachings, students are encouraged to prioritize the common good, resist unethical practices, and advocate for policies that promote equity and sustainability (Ssenyonga, 2018). Moreover, fostering moral responsibility through religious education instills a sense of civic duty among students. As they grapple with moral questions related to governance and economic systems, they become more aware of their roles as responsible citizens. This awareness can inspire them to participate actively in democratic processes, challenge injustices, and contribute to creating more ethical political and economic structures. In this way, religious education serves as a transformative tool, preparing students to engage with the world thoughtfully and ethically.

Further, the results showed that religious education plays a pivotal role in fostering critical thinking and ethical decision-making among students, equipping them to engage meaningfully with political and economic issues. One of the RE teachers revealed that:

“By integrating principles of justice, compassion, and equity into the curriculum, religious education encourages students to reflect on their societal roles and responsibilities. It provides a

moral framework that helps students evaluate political and economic systems critically, emphasizing the importance of fairness and accountability”.

This foundation promotes advocacy for justice, empowering students to address systemic inequalities and champion the rights of marginalized communities.

Through active engagement with religious texts, ethical theories, and case studies, students develop the analytical skills necessary to assess complex societal issues. Religious education emphasizes questioning and dialogue, enabling learners to navigate conflicting perspectives and form well-rounded opinions. This approach nurtures a sense of responsibility to challenge unjust practices and propose sustainable solutions, whether in governance, resource distribution, or economic policies. It instills values that transcend personal interests, encouraging students to prioritize collective well-being and uphold principles of integrity and fairness in their decision-making (Zemni, 2012). Moreover, religious education serves as a platform for exploring real-world applications of ethical principles, such as advocating for human rights, addressing corruption, and promoting social cohesion. By connecting spiritual values to contemporary challenges, it bridges the gap between moral teachings and practical action. This empowers students to not only understand political and economic issues but also to actively participate in shaping a more just and equitable society. Through advocacy projects, debates, and community engagements, students are equipped to become agents of positive change, grounded in a commitment to justice and ethical responsibility (Chanda et al., 2024e).

The study noted that religious education plays a pivotal role in fostering critical thinking and ethical decision-making among students, equipping them to navigate complex political and economic issues. One of the head teachers observed that:

“By engaging with religious teachings, students are encouraged to reflect on fundamental ethical principles such as justice, equity, and compassion”.

These principles often serve as a foundation for active citizenship, guiding learners to critically analyze societal challenges and advocate for solutions rooted in moral and ethical reasoning. Religious education provides a platform for students to explore diverse perspectives, encouraging dialogue and tolerance, which are critical for democratic participation. Zulu (2020) noted that through its focus on moral and ethical frameworks, religious education empowers students to question inequities and injustices in their societies. It promotes critical thinking by challenging learners to assess the ethical implications of political and economic policies and actions. For instance, discussions about stewardship, social responsibility, and the common good help students link religious values to contemporary global issues like poverty, inequality, and environmental sustainability. This approach fosters a sense of responsibility and commitment to societal well-being, motivating students to become engaged citizens who contribute meaningfully to their communities (Mweetwa & Malama, 2016).

Additionally, religious education often incorporates practical activities such as community service, debates, and group projects that simulate real-world problem-solving. These activities not only enhance students' understanding of ethical decision-making but also encourage collaborative efforts to address societal issues. By connecting theoretical knowledge with practical application, religious education nurtures critical thinkers who are adept at balancing individual needs with collective interests. In addressing political and economic issues, religious education can inspire

students to advocate for transparent governance, equitable resource distribution, and inclusive economic policies (Nkandu, 2019). It teaches the importance of ethical leadership and accountability, encouraging students to hold leaders and institutions to high moral standards. This emphasis on ethics and critical thinking prepares students to engage in civic activities such as voting, policy advocacy, and community organizing, thereby reinforcing their role as active citizens dedicated to fostering societal progress. Ultimately, the integration of religious education into the curriculum serves as a powerful tool for promoting active citizenship. By fostering a deeper understanding of ethical principles and critical analysis of societal issues, it enables students to approach political and economic challenges with informed perspectives and a commitment to justice, thereby contributing to a more equitable and sustainable future (Ngulube et al., 2024).

The study also showed that religious education plays a crucial role in nurturing principles of fairness and equity in students, empowering them to critically analyze and ethically respond to political and economic issues. Mweemba (2020) observed that by drawing on moral teachings and ethical frameworks from religious texts and traditions, students are encouraged to reflect on the importance of justice, equality, and the common good. These values, ingrained through religious education, help foster an understanding of societal challenges such as poverty, corruption, and inequality, equipping students to approach these issues with empathy and integrity. Critical thinking is a central skill developed in religious education, as it often involves examining diverse perspectives and questioning established norms. Through discussions on fairness and equity, students learn to challenge biases and prejudices that may influence political and economic systems (Chanda, 2024f). This analytical approach helps students discern ethical implications in policy-making, resource distribution, and leadership decisions, fostering a generation of individuals capable of promoting equitable governance and sustainable development.

Moreover, religious education instills a sense of responsibility and accountability in students, guiding them to make decisions that align with ethical standards. It emphasizes the interconnectedness of all individuals and the importance of considering the well-being of others when addressing political and economic dilemmas (Mawuna, 2017). For instance, lessons on stewardship and communal harmony encourage students to advocate for policies that promote social equity and economic inclusivity, ensuring that marginalized groups are not overlooked in decision-making processes. Mwaura (2019) added that by integrating principles of fairness and equity into its curriculum, religious education not only enhances students' ethical awareness but also prepares them to actively participate in civic life. It inspires them to become agents of positive change, capable of addressing political and economic challenges with a balanced and principled mindset, ultimately contributing to a more just and equitable society.

Figure2: The Role of Religious Education in Fostering Critical Thinking and Ethical Decision-Making among Students Regarding Political and Economic Issues

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are actions that should be taken on the basis of the findings of this study;

1. Integrating Political Economy Concepts into Religious Education Curricula:

- Religious education curricula should incorporate topics that link religious teachings with political and economic principles. This integration can help students understand how ethical and moral frameworks derived from religion can influence governance, leadership, and economic practices.

2. Promoting Interfaith Dialogues and Civic Engagement Programs in Schools:

- Schools should organize interfaith dialogues and civic engagement initiatives that encourage students to explore the practical applications of religious principles in addressing political and economic challenges.

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Authors' Short Biography

	<p>Chanda Chansa Thelma specializes in Education, Political & Social and Sciences. She has lectured and still lecturing at the University level under the school of Humanities, and Social Sciences Education.</p>
	<p>Zohaib Hassan Sain is a Researcher and a Certified Trainer of Total Quality Management, Sustainable Development Goals and Health & Safety.</p>
	<p>Edwin Vinandi Phiri, specializes in Natural Sciences, Adult Education, and Education Management and Administration. He has taught at Secondary Schools for the past 17 years of which 14 years have been spent in Administration.</p>
	<p>Mwila Mwenda Gilbert is an educationist and he has lectured in teacher training colleges for over 20 years now. He specializes in Primary School Teaching Methods.</p>